

MALIBOO: When Machine Learning meets Bayesian Optimization

Bruno Guindani

*Department of Electronics,
Information and Bioengineering
Politecnico di Milano
Milano, Italy*

bruno.guindani@polimi.it

Danilo Ardagna

*Department of Electronics,
Information and Bioengineering
Politecnico di Milano
Milano, Italy*

danilo.ardagna@polimi.it

Alessandra Guglielmi

*Department of Mathematics
Politecnico di Milano
Milano, Italy*

alessandra.guglielmi@polimi.it

Abstract—Bayesian Optimization (BO) is an efficient method for finding optimal cloud computing configurations for several types of applications. On the other hand, Machine Learning (ML) methods can provide useful knowledge about the application at hand thanks to their predicting capabilities. In this paper, we propose a hybrid algorithm that is based on BO and integrates elements from ML techniques, to find the optimal configuration of time-constrained recurring jobs executed in cloud environments. The algorithm is tested by considering edge computing and Apache Spark big data applications. The results we achieve show that our approach reduces the amount of unfeasible executions up to 2-3 times with respect to state-of-the-art techniques.

Index Terms—Cloud computing, Bayesian optimization, Black-box optimization, Machine learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Cloud computing environments are widely employed in several industries, since they allow to easily adjust the allocated resources (CPU, memory, disk, network, etc.) to match the needs of the software application of interest. However, the configuration of these cloud environments is in charge of the end user. A poor choice of software and/or virtual hardware settings can lead to huge additional costs for them, which could have been prevented if a more suitable configuration had been chosen [1], [2]. For instance, the average configuration costs of big data applications can be more than three times as much as the optimal one, and up to 10 times in the worst case [1]. This is especially true for recurring cloud jobs, i.e., applications that need to be executed multiple times, which constitute up to 40% of the total amount of analytic jobs [1], [3]. In these cases, the additional cost of suboptimal configurations piles up over time. It is also important that the execution of a cloud application complies with given time deadlines, either coming from the cloud provider as part of its business model (e.g., Service Level Objectives), or by the end users' needs. Configuration of cloud jobs can heavily impact their running time [2], [4], for better or for worse, and a poor choice of parameters may lead to an out-of-time execution. However, as a consequence of the diverse

behavior and resource requirements of cloud jobs, choosing the best configuration for a broad spectrum of applications is a challenging task.

Bayesian Optimization (BO) has recently gained notoriety as a powerful tool to solve global optimization problems in which expensive, black-box functions are involved [1], [5], [6]. BO is a sequential design strategy that requires few steps to get sufficiently close to the true optimum. BO chooses new points at which to evaluate the function in a such a way to balance exploration (large uncertainty) and exploitation (large expected value) [5].

Machine Learning (ML) models are another popular tool in the world of Information and Communications Technology (ICT) systems. Their remarkable predicting capabilities can assist the user in accurately predicting resource usage, execution times, etc. Indeed, previous work [7]–[13] has shown that ML models are usually able to predict these target quantities with very small validation error.

This paper proposes MALIBOO (MACHINE Learning In Bayesian OptimizatiOn), a tool integrating BO algorithms with ML techniques, with the goal to minimize the execution costs of recurring time-constrained cloud computing jobs. Our approach is validated in a number of scenarios of interest, including edge computing applications and big data analytics. The proposed BO algorithm variants reduce both the unfeasible executions and the percentage of unfeasible costs up to 2-3 times with respect to state-of-the-art techniques.

This paper is organized as follows. Section II surveys the state of the art for both BO and ML techniques, discussing the scenarios they have been applied to. In Section III, we formalize the problem of optimal cloud configuration at hand. Section IV presents an overview of BO and explains its key components. Our contributions involving the integration of ML into BO are detailed in Section V. Finally, we present results for experimental validation of our proposed algorithm in Section VI, and some conclusive comments follow in Section VII.

II. RELATED WORK

In this work, we introduce a new algorithm to find optimal cloud configurations when job execution is subject to time

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constraints. Our main contribution is integrating information coming from ML models in an algorithm based on BO. In this section, we review the state of the art for these techniques.

A. Bayesian Optimization

This work builds on previous results found in [1], in which the *CherryPick* system is applied to optimize the execution of Apache Spark big data applications in cloud computing systems. *CherryPick* exploits pure constrained BO to find optimal cloud configurations.

A recent example of BO being applied to cloud computing is the RAMBO framework presented in [14]. The authors are interested in cloud applications composed of hundreds of microservices, whose resources are allocated optimally via BO. In general, BO has been widely studied for a number of black-box optimization problems [5], ranging from energy minimization for molecule simulation [15] to laser-plasma accelerated electron beams [16].

B. Machine Learning

Our work is motivated by the belief that ML techniques can lend their predicting capabilities to BO to further improve its effectiveness. ML has been widely applied to predict the performance of ICT systems, such as big data applications and training of deep learning models. Overall, results found in literature are promising in showing the usefulness of ML in the context of cloud computing configuration. For instance, [8] examines the performance of several ML models in carrying out predictions of execution times of Apache Spark cloud jobs with different types of workloads. Their results outperform models used by the original creators of Spark. Authors of [9] employ several ML models alongside anomaly detection to properly configure a cloud-based Internet of Things (IoT) device manager while respecting Quality of Service (QoS) constraints. Another recent work, [7] explores performance prediction of training times of GPU-deployed neural networks starting from software/hardware cloud configuration specifications, by using ML techniques and feature selection methods.

C. Machine Learning applied to Bayesian Optimization

Recent ML works involving BO include [17], [18], and [19]. In particular, [19] presents the Paprika scheduler, which is able to jointly optimize hardware and software configurations for Spark workloads. This process uses a BO-based algorithm integrated with ML elements, namely feature selection via Lasso regression. Their model is one of the closest ones to our research quest, but it requires offline training before deployment, which may be not always available, especially for recently released software. Furthermore, its exploitation of ML is arguably limited in scope, since it is only used to choose among the existing features without any regression strategy being involved. Also, authors of [17] and [18] are interested in the deployment of Deep Learning models to limited-capacity edge devices. They propose the SVM-CBO algorithm, which uses ML to approximate the feasible domain under black-box constraints. This approach is arguably inefficient in exploiting

the iteration budget, since it handles separately the domain approximation and optimization phases.

III. PROBLEM OVERVIEW

Our goal is to find the optimal cloud configuration for running an application in a cloud cluster, while abiding by a given time deadline. We consider the mathematical formulation for our constrained, noisy global optimization problem similarly to [1]. Let $x \in \mathcal{A}$ denote the d -dimensional vector representing a configuration for the cloud job, with $\mathcal{A} \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ being the domain of all possible configurations. The vector x can include, e.g., the buffer size, the memory type (SSD vs. HDD), other application-specific parameters (algorithm iterations, number of simulated molecules), and, in particular, the number of total cores (possibly available on multiple homogeneous VMs) used for the job. The *objective function* to be minimized is the total cost $f(x) = P(x)T(x)$. Here, $T(x)$ is the execution time and $P(x)$ is a known, deterministic function representing the price per time unit of configuration x . We also assume the constraint $T(x) \leq T_{max}$, where T_{max} is a given time threshold. Hence, the problem is to find:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{x \in \mathcal{A}} f(x) &= P(x)T(x) + \varepsilon \\ \text{with } \varepsilon &\sim \mathcal{N}(0, \eta^2) \\ \text{s.t. } T(x) &\leq T_{max}, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where ε is a noise term with unknown variance η^2 , which is estimated by log-marginal-likelihood maximization. In an ICT setting, the noise term proves necessary in order to account for the intrinsic variability of execution times, even when the application is run multiple times with the same configuration. This variability is typically produced by external causes, such as access to underlying physical resources or network congestion [1]. In this paper, we assume the deterministic price function $P(x)$ as being proportional to the number of virtual machines or cores used by the application job, which is always included in the cloud configuration vector x .

IV. BAYESIAN OPTIMIZATION BACKGROUND

Within the setting described in Section III, BO is an efficient method because it approximates the minimum \hat{x} of a given black-box objective function $f(\cdot)$ by using as few iterations as possible. Strong assumptions on $f(\cdot)$ are not required, and BO algorithms are derivative-free. For these reasons, BO is often used to optimize expensive black-box functions [1], [5], [6], that is, functions for which little to no information is available, and whose evaluation has significant time, resource, and/or monetary costs. This is exactly the situation at hand with cloud performance optimization, where running many experiments in an attempt to find the optimal configuration would defeat the main purpose of decreasing overall execution costs.

We now give a brief overview on the main tools used by BO. In particular, we shall explain the peculiarities of *Gaussian processes* (Section IV-A) and *acquisition functions* (Sections IV-B and IV-C) in a BO context. Lastly, we summarize this overview in Section IV-D.

A. Gaussian Process

The core idea of BO comes from the Bayesian approach to statistics, in which unknown values are treated as random variables. In this context, a *prior distribution* represents the *a priori* information on the modeled phenomenon – in the case of BO, information on the location of the minimum of $f(\cdot)$. The prior distribution is then iteratively updated with information coming from the observed data, obtaining the *posterior distribution*.

The *Gaussian process* (GP) [20] is the preferred choice for the prior for $f(\cdot)$ in the BO setting. For any $x \in \mathcal{A}$, this prior assigns to the value of $f(x)$ a Gaussian probability distribution which depends on x :

$$f(x) \sim \pi_x(\cdot) = \mathcal{N}(\mu_0(x), \sigma_0^2(x, x)). \quad (2)$$

Functions $\mu_0(\cdot)$ and $\sigma_0^2(\cdot, \cdot)$ are called mean and kernel functions, respectively, and they are the GP model hyperparameters. These functions serve as the “initial guesses” on values of $f(\cdot)$ and on their uncertainty, and they will be iteratively updated with observed values. A constant mean function $\mu_0(\cdot) \equiv \mu_0$ is often adopted, whereas the choice of the kernel is more delicate, since it influences the smoothness of the process. Commonly used kernels include the squared exponential or Radial Basis Function and the Matérn kernel [20]. The former gives the GP an excessively large degree of smoothness, which is unrealistic in many practical scenarios. Therefore, in this work we assume $\mu_0(\cdot) \equiv \mu_0$ and we use the Matérn kernel [5] with smoothness parameter ν :

$$\sigma_0^2(x, x') := \frac{1}{2^{\nu-1}\Gamma(\nu)} \left(\sqrt{2\nu}\|x - x'\| \right)^\nu K_\nu \left(\sqrt{2\nu}\|x - x'\| \right),$$

where $\Gamma(\cdot)$ and $K_\nu(\cdot)$ are the gamma function and the modified Bessel function [21], respectively.

We now examine the posterior distributions for these hyperparameters. Let $H = \{(x_1, f(x_1)), \dots, (x_n, f(x_n))\}$ be the history of n past observations, which we also indicate as H_n when emphasizing its cardinality. Having observed values in H_n , one can compute the posterior distribution of each $f(x)$, starting from the prior distribution in Eq. (2) and taking these observations into account. The posterior is the conditional distribution of $f(x)$ given H_n . In this case, it is a Gaussian distribution with mean $\mu_n(\cdot)$ and variance $\sigma_n^2(\cdot)$:

$$f(x)|H_n \sim \pi_x(\cdot|H_n) = \mathcal{N}(\mu_n(x), \sigma_n^2(x)). \quad (3)$$

Note the conditioning symbol $|$ in Eq. (3). The posterior mean and variance can be computed in closed form by well-known properties of GPs [5]:

$$\mu_n(x) = \mu_0(x) + \sigma_0^2(x, x_{1:n})^T \sigma_0^2(x_{1:n}, x_{1:n})^{-1} \cdot (f(x_{1:n}) - \mu_0(x_{1:n})), \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_n^2(x) = \sigma_0^2(x, x) - \sigma_0^2(x, x_{1:n})^T \sigma_0^2(x_{1:n}, x_{1:n})^{-1} \cdot \sigma_0^2(x, x_{1:n}). \quad (5)$$

In Eqq. (4) and (5), $\sigma_0^2(x, x_{1:n})$ indicates the column vector of values of the $\sigma_0^2(\cdot, \cdot)$ function applied to pairs $(x, x_1), \dots, (x, x_n)$, and similarly for $f(x_{1:n})$ and $\mu_0(x_{1:n})$.

Analogously, $\sigma_0^2(x_{1:n}, x_{1:n})$ is the matrix of values of $\sigma_0^2(x_i, x_j)$ with $i, j = 1, \dots, n$.

Given a configuration x , after n iterations, this probabilistic model allows us to attribute both the current pointwise estimate of $f(x)$ and a measure of uncertainty on such estimate, represented by $\mu_n(x)$ and $\sigma_n^2(x)$ respectively.

B. Acquisition function

We described how BO models the objective function at iteration n . We now move on to explain how BO chooses the next iteration point x_{n+1} based on such model.

At each step, BO formulates a proxy problem – the maximization of the *acquisition function* $g(x)$. This function depends on the GP model at the current algorithm iteration, and measures the utility of evaluating the objective function $f(x)$ in a given configuration x . The acquisition function is optimized at each round of the iterative algorithm, instead of directly optimizing the objective function itself. Indeed, since $g(\cdot)$ is often available in closed form and inexpensive to evaluate, fast heuristics are available to solve this proxy problem.

The acquisition function must strike a delicate balance – the exploration-exploitation trade-off. On one side, we have points to which large uncertainty is attached, for instance because they lie in a region of the domain which has not been explored yet. Choosing such points to evaluate the objective $f(\cdot)$ is appealing, especially early on in the optimization procedure, because this would allow a large decrease of the uncertainty on the position of the optimum. On the other hand, the algorithm does seek to find the optimum of the objective function, therefore it should also choose to evaluate points which most likely (according to the GP model) give small values of $f(\cdot)$. This is done by exploiting the information already available on the location of the optimum, especially in the late iterations of the algorithm.

C. Expected Improvement with Constraints

In this paper, we consider the Expected Improvement acquisition function and its constrained extensions. The *Expected Improvement* (EI) over the best value f_n^* found by the optimization process so far is:

$$EI_n(x) := \mathbb{E}_{\pi_x(\cdot|H_n)}[\max(f_n^* - f(x), 0)] \quad (6)$$

with $f_n^* = \min_{i \leq n} f(x_i)$.

The expectation is taken under the current posterior distribution $\pi(\cdot|H_n)$ of $f(x)$, given history H_n . Eq. (6) means that we maximize the expected value of the improvement over the current best point f_n^* , based on the points in H_n . We now consider a generalization of EI to the constrained optimization setting – the *Expected Improvement with Constraints* (EIC) acquisition function [22]. This function accounts for the probability of a point respecting the constraint indicated in Eq. (1):

$$EIC_n(x) := EI_n(x) \cdot \mathbb{P}_{\pi_x(\cdot|H_n)}(T(x) \leq T_{max}) \quad (7)$$

$$= EI_n(x) \cdot \mathbb{P}_{\pi_x(\cdot|H_n)}(f(x) \leq P(x)T_{max}).$$

In the last equality, we write the constraint $T(x) \leq T_{max}$ as a function of $f(x) = P(x)T(x)$ since the GP prior is placed

on $f(\cdot)$, not on $T(\cdot)$. Finally, note that the EIC in Eq. (7) is the same acquisition function used in *CherryPick* [1].

D. Summary of Bayesian Optimization

The BO procedure is summarized in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Generic Bayesian Optimization algorithm

- 1: choose n_0 initial points
 - 2: evaluate $f(\cdot)$ in the initial points, add evaluations to H
 - 3: **for** iterations $n = 1 : N$ **do**
 - 4: update the current posterior distribution of the GP model with data in H
 - 5: find point x_{n+1} which maximizes the acquisition function $g(\cdot)$ under the current model
 - 6: evaluate $f(x_{n+1})$, add performed evaluation to H
 - 7: **end for**
 - 8: **return** estimated optimum \hat{x}
-

In step 1, a small number n_0 of initial points (i.e., cloud configurations) are selected, usually 3 to 10, in order to initialize the algorithm. These points should be chosen so as to cover the maximum domain area possible, for instance using a Latin hypercube design [23]. We then evaluate these points, i.e., we run the application using these configurations, and we record the points and their evaluations (step 2). After the initialization phase, we enter the algorithm loop, where we update the posterior distribution (step 4), choose the next point x_{n+1} by maximizing the acquisition function (step 5), and evaluate it (step 6). The algorithm stops when the iteration budget N runs out.

Fig. 1 presents a visual summary on how BO works. In

Fig. 1. Bayesian Optimization after 3 iterations.

the top panel, the solid gray line represents the true objective function $f(\cdot)$ to be minimized. We also plot the GP estimates produced by $f(\cdot)$, in terms of its mean function (dashed blue line) and 95% confidence intervals (light blue area). The three red dots represent sampled points, which have smaller uncertainties attached to them with respect to all other domain points (note that utility in such points is still greater than zero if accounting for noise in observations of $f(\cdot)$). As previously explained, the GP model attaches a Gaussian probabilistic estimate to $f(x)$, for each x . In the top panel of the figure, the Gaussian curve in light gray represents this estimate when

$x = 2.51$. In the bottom panel, we plot instead the values of the acquisition function for each value of x . The crossed red point is the one which has been selected to be evaluated in the next round, since it has the largest expected utility among all points in the domain.

V. ENCODING INFORMATION FROM MACHINE LEARNING IN BAYESIAN OPTIMIZATION

Our main contribution is the integration of ML techniques into the BO framework. ML methods can prove to be useful additions in a setting where evaluating the objective function $f(\cdot)$ is expensive. Indeed, a cheap estimation of values of $f(\cdot)$ can make up for the scarcity of direct information on them. In our case, it can be used to convey valuable information about the violation of constraints. Our goal is ultimately to find optimal (or near-optimal) configurations which are also feasible, i.e., points x with $T(x) \leq T_{max}$. Unfeasible points are to be avoided, since they represent a waste of resources in a recurring job setting, providing additional unnecessary costs. As previously stated, the use of ML models is also motivated by their great accuracy in predicting execution times of the applications at hand. Besides the promising results on the matter in the literature [7]–[13], our preliminary analysis shows good prediction capabilities on the target applications, as we shall see in Section VI-D.

A. Novel acquisition functions

The core contribution of MALIBOO is integrating the acquisition function with information coming from ML models. Let $\hat{T}(x)$ be a generic predicting function for $T(x)$, that is, a function which outputs a prediction on the execution time of a cloud job given configuration x . In our case, $\hat{T}(\cdot)$ is a ML regression model trained on all observations H_n collected so far by the BO algorithm. Note that using a model that predicts execution time given configuration x is equivalent to using one predicting the total cost, since they only differ by the known, deterministic constant $P(x)$ (see Eq. (1)).

We propose the following acquisition functions:

- A) $g_A(x) = EIC(x)$: the original Expected Improvement with Constraints acquisition function, used by *CherryPick* [1], which we use as baseline;
- B) $g_B(x) = g_A(x) \cdot \exp(-k \hat{T}(x))$, the latter term being a $[0, 1]$ -valued weight for g_A , and called a nascent minima distribution function [24]. This function serves the purpose of turning $\hat{T}(x)$ into an acquisition-like function. That is, it takes on values close to 1 if the predicted execution time $\hat{T}(x)$ is small (making x a desirable point), and closer to 0 if such prediction is large;
- C) $g_C(x) = g_A(x) \cdot I_{\{\hat{T}(x) \leq T_{max}\}}$, with I being the indicator function: the search is prevented in areas where the current predicted execution time violates the threshold T_{max} . Basically, we use the model $\hat{T}(x)$ to approximate the current feasible domain;
- D) $g_D(x) = g_A(x) \cdot \exp(-k \hat{T}(x)) \cdot I_{\{\hat{T}(x) \leq T_{max}\}}$: the combination of cases B and C.

Note that the original definition of the nascent minima distribution functions (used in variants B and D) includes the normalization constant $1/C_k$ as a multiplicative factor, with $C_k = \int_{\mathcal{A}} \exp(-k\hat{T}(w)) dw > 0$, as described in [24]. However, this value is independent of x , therefore we can omit it when maximizing the acquisition function in x .

B. Proposed algorithm

We summarize the complete procedure implemented in MALIBOO in Algorithm 2. We use a first-in-first-out memory

Algorithm 2 MALIBOO algorithm

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1: choose  $n_0$  initial points
2: evaluate  $f(\cdot)$  in the initial points, add evaluations to  $H$ 
3: for iterations  $n = 1 : N$  do
4:   update the current posterior distribution of the GP
     model with data in  $H$ 
5:   if  $g(\cdot) \neq g_A(\cdot)$  then
6:     train model  $\hat{T}(\cdot)$  with data in  $H$ , to be used in  $g(\cdot)$ 
7:   end if
8:   find point  $x_{n+1}$  which maximizes the acquisition func-
     tion  $g(\cdot)$  under the current model
9:   evaluate  $f(x_{n+1})$ , add performed evaluation to  $H$ 
10:  update memory queue with  $x_{n+1}$ 
11:  if stopping criteria are met then
12:    terminate the algorithm
13:  end if
14: end for
15: return estimated optimum  $\hat{x}$ 

```

queue for discrete features to prevent exploration of already visited values, similarly to the taboo search meta-heuristic methods [25]. In this memory queue, we save the last q points visited by the algorithm. Configurations currently in the queue are excluded from being selected again until they have shifted out of the queue, i.e., after q iterations. Similarly to regular BO, at each round, we maximize the acquisition function of choice, which now incorporates the ML model trained at step 6. Then, we evaluate the newly chosen configuration (step 9) as usual, and we update the aforementioned memory queue (step 10). The algorithm continues until the evaluated running time at the current iteration is sufficiently close to the time threshold: $T(x_n) \in [\alpha T_{max}, T_{max}]$, with $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ (step 12). This is because our goal is to obtain a configuration that is compliant with the time threshold, but also uses as few resources as possible. Generally speaking, using more resources results in a lower execution time – meaning that a time which is just under the threshold likely consumes the least amount of resources for that configuration to be feasible. After termination, it is likely that we have found the true optimal configuration because of the convergence properties of the BO algorithm. Afterwards, we execute subsequent runs using such optimal or near-optimal configuration.

VI. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this section, we present experimental results for validating MALIBOO. In Section VI-A through VI-C, we describe

the applications and cloud settings we consider, as well as the algorithm parameters we use in Section VI-D. The results themselves are explored in detail in Sections VI-E and VI-F.

A. Experiment setting

We test the MALIBOO algorithm on four different scenarios, which act as representatives of different workload types which are relevant to cloud systems. The first three scenarios involve the Apache Spark big data analytics framework [26], while in the fourth one the Stereomatch edge computing application [27] is used. Big data applications are often run on cloud servers because they offer easy access to powerful analysis frameworks such as Apache Spark. On the other hand, an edge computing application represents an emerging access pattern to cloud resources, in which data are collected at the IoT layer, but are processed in the cloud, possibly partially.

B. Apache Spark applications

We now describe the three Spark applications, which are being optimized on the number x of parallel cores used to run them (x is therefore one-dimensional):

- *Query26* is an interactive query from the TPC-DS industry benchmark¹, and represents SQL-like tasks. We execute it with input datasets I of varying size, specifically 250 GB, 750 GB, and 1000 GB.
- *Kmeans* is a well-known ML clustering technique, and a typical example of an iterative task. We execute it on SparkBench² by providing it as input datasets I with 100 features (columns) and varying size (rows): 5, 10, 15, and 20 million.
- *SparkDL Transfer Learning*³ is a big data analytic tool which applies transfer learning to Deep Learning applications, using ML Pipelines from Spark MLlib. In this paper, we consider a binary classification task with input datasets I containing 1000, 1500, and 2500 images.

Spark experiments are conducted on two different computing environments: the Microsoft Azure public cloud, and a private IBM Power8 cluster. In particular, Query26 and SparkDL are executed on Microsoft Azure using the HDInsight service with workers based on 6 D13v2 virtual machines (VMs), each with 8 CPU cores and 56 GB of memory. Instead, Kmeans is run on an IBM Power8 deployment that includes 4 VMs, each with 12 cores and 58 GB of RAM, for a total of 48 CPU cores available for Spark workers, plus a master node with 4 cores and 48 GB of RAM. These two systems are representatives of different computing environments. The Microsoft Azure public cloud is potentially affected by resource contention, and application execution times might experience more variability as a result. Whereas, the private IBM Power8 cluster is fully dedicated to our experiments without any other concurrent activity, i.e., with no resource contention.

For all three Spark applications, we perform one separate experiment for each input dataset I , for a total of 10 experiments. Moreover, for each of these applications, we also

¹<http://www.tpc.org/tpcds>

²<https://codait.github.io/spark-bench>

³<https://github.com/databricks/spark-deep-learning>

carry out one extrapolation experiment. In particular, we fix the largest input dataset I available for each application (1000 GB, 20 million rows, and 2500 images respectively), but we give additional profiling data to the ML model $\hat{T}(\cdot)$ estimating the performance (see Section V-A). These additional profiling data consist of all previous runs with smaller input datasets I (250-750 GB, 5-10-15 million rows, and 1000-1500 images respectively). They are used in the training phase of the regression model $\hat{T}(\cdot)$, in addition to the points in the history H collected by BO. In fact, in a big data setting, it is often required to run data analysis tasks or prediction models on datasets with increasing size. Moreover, provided that the ML model is able to extrapolate accurately, using profiling data from runs with smaller input datasets allows saving on exploratory runs with the larger datasets, which are usually much more expensive. According to preliminary analysis in [8], ML models show indeed good extrapolation capabilities on the applications of interest.

C. Edge computing application

The fourth scenario we consider for validation uses *Stereomatch* [27], an image-processing edge computing application that computes the disparity value between a pair of stereo images (i.e., coming from the same scene but observed by two cameras), which can then be used to calculate the depth of objects in that scene. This application uses adaptive-shape local support windows for each pixel, based on color similarity. In this case, x consists of four independent parameters which influence its execution time: number of parallel cores, color similarity confidence, granularity of the disparity hypotheses to be tested, and length of the arm of the support windows. This is a much larger parameter space than the experiments reported in the previous section, in which we have a mono-dimensional optimization problem on the number of cores only. This application is executed with a fixed input dataset I containing 40 pairs of images, in a Virtual Machine (VM) on a private 32-core server with 64 GB of memory and Ubuntu 20.04. The underlying physical node of this server has two AMD EPYC 7282 processors, with 16 cores and 32 threads, and clock speed 2.8 GHz. Since we use a single input dataset for Stereomatch, we perform a single experiment with it. The total number of experiments we perform across all four scenarios is therefore 14, including the three extrapolation experiments with Spark.

We run MALIBOO on an Ubuntu 20.04 machine with 16 GB RAM for 30 maximum iterations for each experiment, or 60 in the Stereomatch scenario because of the larger search space. Besides the execution time of the job, the computation time for a single algorithm iteration is about 1.5 seconds, with a maximum of 5 seconds for late iterations (in which larger ML models are being trained), and up to 10 seconds for extrapolation experiments.

D. Algorithm settings and evaluation metrics

We compare the four algorithm variants (A-D) in all 14 experiments concerning the four applications described in the

previous section. For each experiment, we use the same initial configurations and time thresholds. In particular, for each experiment, we choose $n_0 = 3$ initial configurations and repeat the experiments with different time thresholds T_{max} . Specifically, for each experiment, we choose a grid of 10 evenly spaced thresholds. This represents an increasingly difficult optimization problem as the time threshold gets smaller, since the feasible domain keeps shrinking.

We use a Ridge linear regression model as the predicting function $\hat{T}(\cdot)$ described in Section V-A. We also provide the model with some additional features derived from the ones in x , namely the inverse of the number of parallel cores, its logarithm (which encodes the cost of reducing operations in parallel frameworks [28]), and the pairwise products of all involved features. This ML model is computationally cheap, and performs better in predicting the performance of the applications of interest when compared to other alternative methods [8]. In particular, we measure its predicting accuracy by computing the Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) of the model: $MAPE(\mathbf{y}, \hat{\mathbf{y}}) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left| \frac{y_i - \hat{y}_i}{y_i} \right|$, where \mathbf{y} is the vector of true values and $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$ is the vector of predictions by the ML model. According to our analysis on the full profiling datasets, the test-set MAPE of the chosen model is almost always lower than 9%. Even when just a small handful of training points is available, errors are mostly within 20%.

As for the GP hyperparameters, as described in Section IV, we choose a constant mean function and a Matérn kernel with smoothness parameter $\nu = 5/2$. We choose $k = 2$ as the exponential term used in variants B and D, $q = 10$ as the length of the memory queue, and $\alpha = 0.9$ as the lower bound parameter for the stopping criterion.

We now compare our proposed algorithm variants (B-D) with the baseline variant A, in terms of number of unfeasible runs and their cumulative costs. Variant A coincides with constrained pure BO using the EIC acquisition function, i.e., the technique used by *CherryPick* [1].

E. Numerical results

The first four rows of Table I summarize the results on the four applications of interest, averaged over the varying input data sizes and time thresholds. In particular, we report: the number of executions which selected an unfeasible configuration; the percentage of costs (the $f(x)$ in Eq. (1)) coming from unfeasible configurations over the total amount of costs; and the average cost among feasible configurations, normalized over the cost of variant A. For the Query26 application, our algorithm variants reduce the unfeasible executions and the ratio of unfeasible costs two to three times with respect to pure BO (variant A). The average cost of a feasible configuration is also reduced. On average, in the three Spark applications, we see an average improvement of 2.2 times on the number of unfeasible runs, and about two times on the total unfeasible cost. The cost of feasible runs improves by 10% on average, and it is always at least competitive with variant A in the worst case. As for the multidimensional case with the Stereomatch application, results are in line with the other three scenarios,

TABLE I
MEASURED METRICS FOR VARIANTS A-D OF THE PROPOSED ALGORITHM

scenario	var. A	var. B	var. C	var. D
Query26				
unfeasible runs	11.23	4.34	4.11	4.31
ratio of unfeasible costs	0.36	0.14	0.13	0.14
norm. mean feasible cost	1.00	0.87	0.87	0.88
Kmeans				
unfeasible runs	10.52	5.74	5.93	5.96
ratio of unfeasible costs	0.34	0.20	0.21	0.21
norm. mean feasible cost	1.00	1.00	1.01	1.00
SparkDL				
unfeasible runs	11.65	5.29	5.14	5.24
ratio of unfeasible costs	0.32	0.16	0.15	0.16
norm. mean feasible cost	1.00	0.83	0.87	0.79
Stereomatch				
unfeasible runs	18.87	13.83	10.83	8.70
ratio of unfeasible costs	0.27	0.22	0.17	0.15
norm. mean feasible cost	1.00	0.78	0.86	0.69
Query26-extrapolation				
unfeasible runs	3.57	4.64	4.64	4.86
ratio of unfeasible costs	0.11	0.15	0.15	0.15
norm. mean feasible cost	1.00	0.83	0.83	0.83
Kmeans-extrapolation				
unfeasible runs	10.00	5.00	5.00	5.00
ratio of unfeasible costs	0.33	0.17	0.17	0.17
norm. mean feasible cost	1.00	1.33	1.40	1.32
SparkDL-extrapolation				
unfeasible runs	12.75	8.62	6.29	5.57
ratio of unfeasible costs	0.35	0.27	0.19	0.16
norm. mean feasible cost	1.00	0.98	0.83	1.13

with the average improvement on feasible costs further increasing to about 25%.

A representative example for a run of our proposed algorithm is displayed in Fig. 2, which represents the Query26 scenario. In the left panel, we represent the number of cores chosen at each algorithm iteration. The green horizontal line is the true optimum of the constrained optimization problem, which we identified by inspection through an exhaustive profiling of the application. The vertical, dashed red line indicates the run at which the stopping criterion kicks in, and after which we stick to the best configuration found so far by the algorithm. In the center panel, a rectangle represents a single run, with its sides being the execution time of the job (horizontal side) and the number of cores (vertical side). Therefore, the area of a rectangle is proportional to the execution cost $f(x)$ for that particular run (see Eq. (1)). We highlight in red the rectangles corresponding to unfeasible configurations. Finally, the signed percentage errors of the ML model for the execution time are displayed in the right panel. As previously mentioned, at each iteration, the model is trained with all data from previous iterations, and the error is evaluated on the new configuration chosen by the algorithm. We see that after one initial iteration with a large error, our ML models quickly converge to errors very close to zero. The initial spike is explained by the fact that the BO algorithm is still in the exploration phase, and selects a configuration with a large amount of cores since that region of the domain is still unexplored. This also means that the ML model struggles in the first iteration, since it was trained with data with small

Fig. 2. Query26: comparison of pure BO (variant A) with variants B-D.

Fig. 3. Kmeans: comparison of pure BO (variant A) with variants B-D.

Fig. 4. Comparison between runs without additional data (left) and ones with additional extrapolation data (right).

amounts of cores. After that, the ML model has accumulated enough information to achieve good predicting capabilities. As was shown in Table I, from Fig. 2, it is clear that our algorithm drastically reduces the number of unfeasible runs (from 10 to only 1-2) while still achieving the optimum.

We show a similar plot for the Kmeans application in Fig. 3. Note that, despite the ML model being less accurate on the Kmeans application when compared to other workloads (about 20% MAPE before convergence, compared to less than 9% for Query26), results are still in line with the other cases. Overall, our algorithm variants converge to an optimal number of cores (or to a feasible near-optimal one, i.e., one more or one less than the optimum) over 54% of the times within the given iteration budget, usually before the 10th execution. Variant A (i.e., pure constrained BO) achieves a similar percentage in the Query26 and Kmeans experiments, but fails to converge to a feasible near-optimal configuration in all experiments involving the SparkDL and Stereomatch applications.

F. Extrapolation runs with additional data

We also perform extrapolation experiments with the three Apache Spark applications: Query26, Kmeans, and SparkDL. We recall that these experiments are performed by providing additional profiling data from smaller datasets to the ML model in the training phase.

A representative extrapolation result is shown on the right side of Fig. 4, while the left side reports the corresponding case with “vanilla” algorithms, without additional training data being fed to the ML models. (Variant A is identical on both sides, since pure BO does not use any ML model.)

One can immediately notice the lack of the initial spike in the error diagrams of variants B-D, owing to the fact that the ML model is trained with more data points from the very beginning. Thanks to the aforementioned good extrapolation capabilities, the ML model is able to accurately predict the execution time, even for a point from a region that the BO algorithm has not explored yet. Results of all runs averaged over the varying time thresholds are collected in the bottom three rows of Table I.

In general, the algorithm with additional data has a more aggressive search behavior, trading off a small amount of unfeasible runs (2 at most) for a lower average cost of individual runs (6 to 26%). This is explained by the additional data making the trained ML model more accurate. The model guides the domain exploration of BO towards more promising points, either because of their lower predicted execution time (variant B), their predicted feasibility (variant C), or both (variant D). These points are thus more likely to be on the boundary of the feasibility region of the optimization problem, where the value of the objective function is close to the

optimum, but also where we have a higher risk of slipping out of the feasibility region. The extrapolation version of MALIBOO is therefore best suited for the user with a lower risk aversion.

In conclusion, each of our algorithm variants (B-D) outperforms the constrained vanilla BO technique in [1] (here represented by variant A) with respect to multiple metrics: number of unfeasible runs, total amount of unfeasible costs (two to three times less), and average cost of the unfeasible configuration (13 to 22% less).

VII. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we have presented MALIBOO, a tool combining a BO algorithm with ML techniques, to find the optimal configuration for a recurring job running in the cloud, under a given time threshold. Results on tested edge computing and big data analysis applications have shown that our algorithm significantly reduces the amount of unfeasible executions with respect to a pure BO approach, as well as reducing the average cost of the configuration. Overall, each of our algorithm variants outperforms the state-of-the-art BO technique used as benchmark.

We plan on testing the hybrid algorithm implemented by MALIBOO on other application domains, e.g., High-Performance Computing systems and Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications, while also considering acquisition functions suitable for a parallel exploration of alternative configurations.

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